

Acrida sp., *Acrotylus humbertianus* Sauss, *Atractomorpha acutipennis* (Guer.), *Calliptamus* sp., *Catantops pinguis* Stal., *Chroedicus illustris* Wlk., *Eyprepocnemis plorans* Charp, *Shirakiacris shirakii* I. Bol., *Oedaleus abruptus* Thunb., and *Truxalis grandis* Dirsh are also found on rice but in low numbers.

Grasshoppers are more serious in the rice nurseries where young nymphs accumulate in large numbers and damage the seedlings. In some cases almost the whole of a nursery plot is destroyed. Plowing of fields and digging of embankments during winter seem good control measures because they destroy most of the egg pods. ❧

Insecticidal control of the brown planthopper in the field

P. Narayanasamy and M. Balasubramanian, Division of Plant Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University, Annamalaiagar, India

Field studies on the efficacy of insecticides against the rice brown

planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* showed that the maximum reduction of insect numbers occurred in plots treated with carbofuran 3% G (2.25 kg a.i./ha), followed by that in plots treated with methamidophos (0.1% spray), Phorate (2.25 kg a.i./ha), and phoxim (0.05% spray). In general, mephosfolan 10% G was found to be ineffective. ❧

Effect of paddy-water and foliar applications of insecticides on brown planthopper populations 9–12 weeks after transplanting, Annamalaiagar, India, kuruvai, 1973.

Treatment ^a	Application rate (kg a.i./ha)	Planthoppers ^b (no./hill)					Change from control level (%)
		9 wk	10 wk	11 wk	12 wk	Mean	
Carbofuran granules	0.75	0	61	27	28	29	- 67
	1.50	0	0	0	44	11	- 88
	2.25	0	0	0	0	0	- 100
Phorate granules	0.75	5	39	121	143	77	- 13
	1.50	6	33	153	156	87	- 2
	2.25	3	13	62	71	37	- 58
Mephosfolan granules	0.75	2	58	160	128	87	- 2
	1.50	3	132	123	125	96	+ 8
	2.25	4	20	122	122	92	+ 4
Methamidophos spray	0.025%	3	17	62	61	41	- 54
	0.05%	4	2	111	88	51	- 42
	0.1%	7	18	46	76	37	- 58
Phoxim spray	0.025%	4	37	128	131	73	- 17
	0.05%	2	45	78	76	50	- 43
	0.1%	4	77	99	92	68	- 23
Control	-	13	48	132	143	89

^aChemicals applied on 15th and 45th days after transplanting; treatments significant at 1% level (C.D. = 1.741).

^bAv. of 20 hills.

Research on pests of rice in Malawi (Central Africa)

H. R. Feijen, University of Malawi, Zomba, Malawi. Present address: Universidad Eduardo Mondlane, Maputo, Mozambique

From 1971 until 1975 a research project was conducted to determine the relative importance of various insect pests of rice in Malawi.

The most numerous insect pest of rice is the stem borer *Diopsis thoracica* Westwood (Diptera; Diopsidae). Other diopsids are unimportant. Lepidopterous

stem borers, such as *Maliarpha separatella* Rag., *Chilo partellus* (Swinh.), *Chilo diffusilineus* (de Joannis), *Sesamia calamistas* (Hamps.), *Schoenobius* sp., and *Thopeutis* spp., are of little importance, since they are controlled by many parasitoids. At the end of prolonged rainy seasons, fields planted late were attacked by the rice gall midge *Orseola oryzae* (Wood-Mason).

Three larval parasitoids kept that pest under control. Several outbreaks of the rice beetle *Trichispa sericea* (Guer.), occurred in rice fields with high water

levels. In the 1972–73 season several hectares of nurseries were destroyed by this species. However, parasitoids usually kept the beetle under control. Other pests of minor importance were lepidopterous defoliators such as *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guen.), *Spodoptera cilium* Guen., *Diacrisia scortillum* (Wllgr.), *Borbo borbonica* (Boisd.), *Grammodes geometrica* F., *Mythimna* sp. and *Brachmia* sp., the green rice bug *Nezara viridula* (L.), and the mole cricket *Gryllotalpa africana* (P. de Beauv.).

Most of the Lepidoptera were identified by Dr. P. E. S. Whalley and Dr. I. W. B. Nye of the British Museum (Natural History).

The project formed part of the Lake Chilwa Coordinated Research Project and was financed by the Netherlands Foundation for the Advancement of Tropical Research (WOTRO), and the Research Council of the University of Malawi. ❧

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Weed competition in transplanted rice

Sadeli Suriapermana, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Sukamandi, Indonesia

To study the effect of various weeds in season-long competition with IR34, the desired weed species were sown with the rice at transplanting. Then at regular intervals all weeds, except the species under study, were removed.

All weeds except *Salvinia natans* caused yield losses (see table). The losses ranged from 19% (with competition from *Marsilea minuta*) to 43% (with competition from *Fimbristylis* sp. and *Echinochloa colona*). Losses were greater when competition was from more than one weed. The greatest loss (55%) occurred in the unweeded check plot, where all the tested weed species and the natural weed population competed simultaneously against rice.

Surprisingly, in the plots with competition from *S. natans*, which is regarded as a major problem in rice fields in Java, yields were slightly higher and the number of productive tillers was 19% higher than in the weed-free check.

It is not known why, but the weight of *S. natans* competing with rice was lower than that of other weeds, and it is possible that the weed, which rapidly covers the surface of the water, reduced volatilization losses of applied nitrogen.

Effect of competition from various weed species on number of productive tillers and grain yield of transplanted rice IR34.

Competing weed species	Weed weight 70 DT ^a (t/ha)	Productive rice tillers (no./hill)	Rice yield (t/ha)
<i>Salvinia natans</i>	16.0	1.0	4.4
None	13.4	0	4.2
<i>Marsilea minuta</i>	13.7	2.5	3.4
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	11.2	1.4	3.1
<i>Cyperus</i> sp.	9.6	4.5	2.9
<i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	9.3	4.6	2.4
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	7.1	7.6	2.4
<i>M. vaginalis</i> + <i>Cyperus</i> sp.	7.5	9.8	2.3
<i>Cyperus</i> sp. + <i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	8.0	8.9	2.3
<i>M. vaginalis</i> + <i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	7.6	6.3	2.0
All + natural weed flora	8.8	6.5	1.9

^aDT = days after transplanting.

Treatments showed no significant differences in number of panicles per hill. The urea treatment showed the greatest number of grains per panicle, closely followed by *Azolla*-plus-fertilizer. The two *Azolla* treatments outdid the urea treatment in percentage of filled grains. *Azolla*-plus-fertilizer registered 132% as many filled grains per panicle as the control; the urea treatment registered 95%. Perhaps the *Azolla* treatment reduced sterility; further study of that question would be needed before drawing such a conclusion, however. The results clearly indicate that *Azolla* has a beneficial effect on yield of this rice variety.

Sulfur responses of lowland rice in South Sulawesi, Indonesia

C. P. Mamaril, G. J. Blair, E. O. Momuat, Ch. S. Momuat, and A. Pangerang Umar, Lembaga Penelitian Pertanian Maros, P. O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, Sulawesi Selatan, Indonesia

In many areas of South Sulawesi, Indonesia, farmers report little or no response of rice to urea in nitrogen-deficient areas. Because sulfur deficiency is the likely cause, studies of the response to ammonium sulfate were begun in 1976 (see table).

A decrease in the number of tillers was the major cause of yield reduction in sulfur-deficient plants. The plants showed yellowing of new growth. Symptoms generally were not uniform throughout a paddy; they were milder in areas with less waterlogging. To alleviate the problem farmers often drain paddies — a risky practice where there may not be sufficient water supply until harvest.

Response of lowland rice to additions of sulfur.

Site	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Control	Urea ^a	Ammonium sulfate
1	1.13	2.55	3.57
2	0.73	3.52	4.49
3	3.04	3.59	5.22
4	4.83	5.05	4.78
5	2.75	4.05	5.35
6	2.63	3.99	4.46
7	2.28	3.00	2.45
8	2.66	5.64	3.50

^aEqual rates of nitrogen.

Soil and crop management

Azolla utilization in rice culture

I. Watanabe, soil microbiologist, International Rice Research Institute

Azolla can grow on nitrogen-free media with the aid of the nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae*.

Under suitable conditions, it doubles its weight in 3 to 5 days by fixing 0.45 to 0.57 mg N/g fresh weight each day. Phosphorus, calcium, and iron are critical macronutrients in the water culture of *Azolla*. Temperatures above 31 °C inhibit its growth. *Azolla* that grew in field plots for 20 to 23 days accumulated about 24 kg N/ha. From October to January (106 days), five crops of *Azolla* were harvested, accumulating 120 kg N/ha.

Azolla nitrogen was released slowly; its availability to a single rice crop was about 70% of that of nitrogen from ammonium sulfate. A field was inoculated with *Azolla* at the time of transplanting of dry-season rice. Adding superphosphate improved *Azolla* growth; 40 days later the *Azolla* covered the surface and was incorporated into the

soil with a hand weeder. The result was a 13% increase in grain yield over a plot that was puddled in midseason without *Azolla*.

Effect of *Azolla* on yield of rice

S. A. Kulasooriya and R. S. Y. de Silva Department of Botany Peridenya Campus, University of Sri Lanka

The effect of *Azolla* on rice yield was compared with the effect of urea fertilizer. Four treatments were used on rice variety BG 77-11 transplanted when 3 weeks old into 15-sq m plots:

- (1) control — no *Azolla*, no fertilizer;
- (2) *Azolla*, no fertilizer;
- (3) *Azolla* + a fertilizer mixture of phosphorus (67.3 kg/ha), potassium (43 kg/ha), and molybdenum (5.04 kg/ha); and
- (4) phosphorus, potassium, and molybdenum with urea (89.7 kg nitrogen/ha). When *Azolla* was used, it was inoculated 3 weeks before transplanting at 150 g/plot and again 1 week after transplanting. The urea was applied in three doses, 1, 5, and 9 weeks after transplanting.